

MATHEMATICS EDUCATION IN THE “NEW CLIMATIC REGIME”

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MEI 7 proposes to explore the topic of mathematical literacy throughout and beyond education. The topic invites us to connect learners’ engagement with mathematics in the formal settings of education and the proficiency to work with the tools of mathematics in unexpected ways in a variety of contexts outside of such formal settings. The notion of mathematical literacy proposed in the call of the conference emphasizes citizenship and access, as well as the importance of mathematical literacy for engagement with society today and in the future. Mathematics education and mathematics education research are important not only for promoting mathematical literacy for all, but also for showing new directions for advancing this intention in Ireland. The relationship among researchers in the country and with the international field of mathematics education research is a way of supporting such an aim.

There are many possibilities to address the topic of mathematical literacy following the lines sketched in the conference call. Given my research on the cultural politics of mathematics education (e.g., Valero, 2018), I would like to contribute to the conference by discussing how mathematics education relates to the “New Climatic Regime” (Latour, 2017). Here I sketch aspects of an argument that serves as an invitation to reinvent different notions of mathematics education and of mathematics literacy.

THE “NEW CLIMATIC REGIME”

A mathematics education that engages people —young as well as old— with relevant mathematical literacy talks to the world that people live in. For a long time there have been efforts to create a connection between the happenings in the classroom and the “reality” outside of school. Different forms of pedagogies have tried to “bring reality to the classroom” as a way to generate a link that can promote meaningful learning that can prepare learners to be able to bring what is learned to other contexts of life, study and work (e.g., Gravemeijer, 1994). Even if some success can be documented, still failure to do so is more frequent than desired, or at least so can be argued to be the case if we take results of school achievement that claim to measure students’ competence to use mathematics to solve real life problems, such as OECD’s PISA studies interested in finding out “what is important for citizens to know and be able to do?” (OECD, 2018, p. 3).

I would like to stop and ask: What is that “real” world that we have now out of school, for which governments and educators alike claim to be preparing new generations to act in? Is it an international competitive market economy? Is it a world of decision-making? Is it that of rapidly changing technology and uncertainty? Is it one of hope, democracy and equal opportunities for all?

In his recent essay “Down to Earth: Politics in the New Climatic Regime”, Bruno Latour takes a critical and unexpected look at current events such as the revival of populist

nationalisms around the world, the deregulations of globalization, the increase in poverty and inequalities, and the denial of “climate change” understood in a broad sense as the “relations between humans and the material conditions of their existence” (Latour, 2018, p. 1). He argues that looking at these phenomena as distinct, separate trends does not allow us to recognize the conditions and politics of the moment, where the ruling classes seem to act as if there is not a possible common future for them and for all others on Earth. Divisions and tensions are evident all around, and what had been the promises of a better life for all seem to be at stake. Thus, understanding the configuration of what he calls the “New Climatic Regime” —the situation “in which the physical framework that the Moderns had taken for granted, the ground on which their history had always been played out, has become unstable (Latour, 2017, p. 3)— is a way of figuring possibilities for a new political standpoint. To have a political standpoint is a matter that concerns educational thinking and the philosophy of mathematics education, since the question of the direction that such education may take is not an intrinsic matter that is defined a priori by what one may consider to be the mathematical content of education.

The New Climatic Regime is not only the unavoidable recognition that the material conditions of our existence as humans, what we have called “nature”, is about to break down in a way that seriously threatens the viability of the way in which we have lived. It is also the fact that the ways in which we have conceived of “nature”, “science”, “politics” and even the “human” are no longer sustainable. The ideas that since the Enlightenment have dominated the Western rationality to drive humans towards progress and to reach a more desirable future can no longer be maintained in uncritical manners. That the planet almost “turns against us” is no other than the clear sign that the assumed separation of the natural, on the one hand, and the human and culture, on the other hand, is urgently up to revision. The issues of “climate change” are part of political discussions that entangle increasing inequality, poverty and expansion of wealth; migrations, immigrants and the protection of borders, as well as sustainability, CO₂ emissions and aggressive exploitation of natural resources. Latour’s idea of a New Climatic Regime is a call to think and act seriously on the basic assumptions that inform the wicked times that we live in.

One could be tempted to pose the question that if this is the situation, then what should mathematics education provide to citizens for coping successfully in a New Climatic Regime? This is the typical question that education in general and mathematics education in particular has always posed. In Modernity, education has served as the governing strategy to solve social problems. This is what historians of education call the “educationalization of social problems” (e.g., Tröhler, 2017). Thus, there is an established idea that education should always respond to the problems of the present to offer solutions to the future by preparing citizens to deal with a future. This has been a strong narrative that can be easily identified in mathematics education. One current example is the identification of programming as a capacity needed for the future workforce, and a current and future lack of qualified persons to do programming according to the expected trends for what will produce value. As a result, many governments suggest to include programming in the school curricula, and this results in initiatives such as one of the most recent changes to the Swedish school curriculum that asks mathematics teachers to incorporate programming as part of mathematics teaching.

But this move would be to continue the same logic that has led us to the current situation. The interesting question, inspired in the Latourian proposal, would be to ask: In which ways is mathematics education now and in the past entangled in the network of people, institutions and materialities that support our current ways of making and thinking about the world? How does mathematics education offer an insight to find an orientation in a world where there seems not to be a common ground? Of course, some critical voices (e.g., Lundin, 2012; Pais, 2012) would call attention on the arrogance of mathematics educators to think that indeed our research and the practices of teaching and learning may offer possibilities of addressing injustice, differentiation, poverty, personal or national success... I would humbly say that as far as mathematics in the school curriculum is increasingly used as an effective biopolitical technology to govern people and populations (e.g., Valero & Knijnik, 2016), the issue of which ideas of us as historical subjects and of the world mathematics teaching and learning is effecting should be a topic of discussion and thinking.

To put in other more familiar terms, mathematics education research has kept a line of reflection on the problem of justification of mathematics education as an area of teaching and learning. More than 20 years ago, Niss (1996) reflected on the multiple reasons that justify the implicit and explicit goals for mathematics education. The cultural reason of learning part of human knowledge creation, the political reason of preparing for citizenship and the economic reasons of qualification for productive functions that Niss identified continue to be present in the way that we conceive of mathematics education and its role in the making of mathematically literate people. Many other proposals of what may count as mathematical literacy or competence have been present in the field. Some emphasize some aspects more than others, but more or less there is an agreement in these basic justifications for why mathematics education. After all, the field of mathematics education research builds on the assumption that Mathematics is still the “queen of the sciences” and that school mathematics is of paramount importance. Our narratives tend to be fixed and stable, and to privilege the intention of being ambassadors for Mathematics.

So far, however, few mathematics educators engage with contemporary philosophical discussions on how science, mathematics and society have changed, and with different possibilities for imagining what may count as mathematical literacy in current times. An example could be the recent book edited by de Freitas, Sinclair and Coles (2017). Expanding the intellectual quest for what is and counts as mathematical in multiple sites of culture, beyond the limits of well-established narratives of Mathematics and of mathematics education, is an important task as we continue to consider the justifications and the overall enterprise of mathematics education. In particular, I am interested in asking not the question of how we should think of mathematics education for the future, but of understanding the configuration of what we consider to be mathematics education, the assumptions that have been familiarized to the point that we consider them to be necessary truths.

MATHEMATICS AND THE MAKING OF THE MODERN CITIZEN

Education through school as an institution has been an effective mechanism of Modern government that relies on knowledge to legitimize power. Within school, mathematics education has historically provided not only knowledge, abilities and possibilities of cognitive

development for children; it has most of all provided ways of understanding oneself as a historical subject with and through school mathematics. Studies of learning as change in identity have shown how learners, in the context of the practices of teaching and learning of mathematics, become certain types of persons and this is because knowing is not simply an objectification of knowledge, it is inseparably also a process of subjectification, to use Radford's terms (Radford, 2008).

Studies that have focused on the subjectification that takes place in mathematics education have argued that the routines and procedures in classrooms, while making available a content to acquire, also teach children how to be rational and ordered, how to classify and rank, how to be objective and restrain his/her subject position to produce a detached form of talking about the objects and ideas being manipulated, to desire progress, advancement and growth and even more recently competition and entrepreneurship etc. (e.g., Walkerdine, 1988; Popkewitz, 2004; Andrade-Molina & Valero, 2017; Diaz, 2017; Llewellyn, 2018). If mathematics education indeed builds the discursive and material frame for children to objectify the cultural objects of mathematics and at the same time gain the characteristics of mind, spirit and reason that make the culture of those objects, then mathematics education is an effective technology of governing populations towards being Modern. Of course, this does not mean that each one single individual will indeed be a perfectly designed tin soldier. The point is that we all would have passed through many years of mathematics education that has inserted in our mind, body and forms of thinking important elements of the Modern being. This is not just an oppression. This is also a very productive force to make the type of societies that we have had so far...for good and for bad.

THE LIMITS OF MODERNITY AND OF MATHEMATICS EDUCATION

The use of the expression the “New Climatic Regime” is a way for Latour to playfully indicate that the “New Regime” —the project that the Enlightenment and Modernity brought forward to replace the “Old Regime” of political tyranny based on the authority granted by God— is in urgent need of revision. Knowledge of scientific type, for men to tame nature, was expected to bring a new form of government, a new order, a new hope for the future. The problem is now that we are in the presence of the limits of the project of modernity itself: The forms of production, knowledge, exchange and life are called to question to the extent that no possible project of “modernization” of any nation, developed or developing, can be achieved as planned because there will be no Earth on which to fulfil it.

The predicament for mathematics education emerges when its whole enterprise is geared towards producing modern subjectivities in a time when insisting on continuing to be Modern is a death sentence for the Earth —humans included. This statement can generate questions in very many directions: So, tell us, which contents should then be taught? Which kind of pedagogy should we now bring —to teach the canonical contents of the mathematics curriculum— so that children care for the Earth? What is the mathematics education for a future...if there is a possible future? As I said, I will resist the temptation of following this path; instead, I delve into the configuration of mathematics education as a Modern enterprise with the hope that we can find new possibilities for other articulations of content, curricula and pedagogies. There is a series of ideas that can be called into question. Suffice to say that

each one of these deserves a detailed investigation and some of them have indeed already been explored. Here I will only point to some key issues.

Mathematics resides in the mind and makes the good thinker. One of the strongest ideas in current culture is the assumption that mind, thinking and mathematics are connected; and that the materiality of the body is either not important or a simple tool for mathematical thinking. This idea has been challenged (e.g., Lakoff & Núñez, 2000). More recently, de Freitas and Sinclair (2014) have proposed to bring new materialist philosophies to think of the body in/of mathematics. The questioning challenges the duality body/mind that is part of the Western rationalist culture. This duality is also connected to the nature/culture divide that separates the world of the matter from the world of the human. If humans are the superior creation of God and are given the unique capacity to think (and the thinking is in the mind), their mind and ideas produce the possibilities of culture, even the study of nature and its control for the benefit of humanity itself. What is physical or material in nature is to be studied and perceived by the disciplining of the mind. These dualities, so entrenched in the Western, rationalist, Modern epistemology, are at the core of how we conceive of learning and of how we conceive of mathematics as a tool of knowledge that humans have, to distance themselves from the world of nature. In the New Climate Regime Latour proposes that an important realization is that nature and culture are not separated as distinct entities: they are intertwined.

Mathematics is universal and it makes the homeless mind. Another idea about mathematics is that it deals with universal abstractions. When taught in school it should provide people with the capacity to operate on objects and processes on the grounds of true valid rules, in a numerical and symbolic language that transcends the diversity and shortcomings of natural languages and localities. Against a notion of the particular and local, a cosmopolitan form of reason based on mathematics and science fabricates a *homeless mind*, an individuality that sees itself in “relation to transcendental categories that seem to have no particular historical location or author to establish a home” (Popkewitz, 2008, p. 30). Subjects who embody a homeless mind are necessary for moving the desire for a globalized progress. In the New Climatic Regime Latour calls to question the relationship between the global and the local to rethink the role of the territory in a new configuration of threats of environmental, economic and populational type.

Mathematics is a superior creation of dominant cultures and it cannot be acquired by the “Other”. As a privileged form of knowledge of the white, Western culture, mathematics has emerged entangled with political power and the “problem of democracy” which is the establishment of rational means for distributing resources and goods to those who are members of a society (Rose, 1991), be it within the nation or among nations and territories. To produce and know mathematics—and science—has been taken to be a characteristic of the “advanced” cultures and individuals. Thus, the distribution of mathematical competence at individual, community or national levels has been an effective power mechanism to determine who is worthy to have access to different opportunities in society. The persistence of the inequality of access and achievement is connected to the assumption of the epistemic disadvantage of the “Other” (Valero, 2018). In a New Climatic Regime, the increase in inequalities and the explosion of poverty endanger the life opportunities of many people and

of the planet itself. How can mathematics education challenge the assumption of the epistemic disadvantage and inequality in inventing new forms of relations with/in mathematics?

NEW POSSIBILITIES?

Latour's hypothesis of the current New Climatic Regime challenges many key ideas and practices that have been taken for granted and that are at the core of assumptions in what constitutes mathematics and school mathematics as cultural forms of thinking, knowing and being. I have pointed here to three such ideas. One could also identify many more, such as the idea that mathematics creates growth and that such growth manifests in increasing economic wealth—an idea that at the moment manifests in the close link between the production of mathematics and science and the strengthening of current financial capitalism (e.g., Valero, 2017). A series of questions for mathematics education can be raised in an attempt to engage with the responsibility of researchers and educators to imagine new possibilities for practice. For example: Can we imagine of ways of reinventing what counts as mathematical beyond the body/mind, nature/culture divide; or to challenge the universalism of abstraction to link to the locality of thinking; or to leave behind assumptions of deficit in different cultures; or to embrace a mathematics of de-growth? When I say here "practice" I am not only thinking about what may actually happen in classrooms, but also and foremost on the intellectual activity of thinking seriously what is and could be the components of a mathematical literacy in a New Climatic Regime. The question is open and far from being exhausted.

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